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California State University, Fullerton
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Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia

IMPROVING INFORMED CONSENT FOR EPIDURAL ANESTHESIA TO INCLUDE
POSTDURAL HEADACHE EDUCATION

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Purpose/Objectives - The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice scholarly project was to improve the epidural informed consent process for CRNAs at Kaiser Permanente San Bernardino County by implementing an educational module emphasizing a standardized epidural informed consent to include PDPH education for laboring parturients. **Background** - CRNAs are ethically responsible for informed consent for all procedures. Parturients are a unique challenge to obtaining informed consent due to the labor process and its environment. Lack of standardization for obtaining informed consent from this population can lead to unintentional omission of risks of the procedure, including postdural puncture headache. **Methodology** - This was a pilot study with data collected At Kaiser San Bernardino County from September 6, 2023 to November 19, 2023. Participants were 15 CRNAs (n=15) that worked the most OB CRNA shifts from April 2022 to April 2023. Pre-post intervention evaluation was based on an abstraction tool and suggested scoring approach developed by the British Journal of Medicine. A paired t-test statistical analysis compared pre-education module consent scores with post-education module scores. **Results** - The difference between the pre-education module scores and the post-education module scores was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). Additionally, there was no correlation between the participant's demographic data and their pre- and post-intervention scores, including how many years worked as a CRNA. Thus, standardization of informed consent processes improved the quality of informed consent, increasing patient education on postdural puncture headaches.

Keywords: informed consent, epidural anesthesia informed consent, education module for nurse anesthetists, postdural puncture headache

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Background

Certified registered nurse anesthetists (CRNAs) must obtain informed consent for all anesthetic procedures or are ethically responsible for ensuring that a qualified anesthesia provider has obtained informed consent (American Association of Nurse Anesthetists [AANA], 2016). Informed consent for the obstetric population poses a unique challenge to the CRNA as it is generally obtained during the patient's labor process. Obtaining informed consent while a parturient is experiencing pain or distress may result in the anesthesia provider excluding explaining the risks associated with neuraxial labor analgesia, such as postdural puncture sequelae (Trumble et al., 2015).

A postdural puncture headache (PDPH) is one of the serious risks discussed during informed consent for neuraxial labor anesthesia (Vallejo & Zakowski, 2022). Without thorough patient education during informed consent on the symptoms, diagnosis, and treatment of PDPH, postpartum patients are at risk for delayed treatment and complications of PDPH, including subdural hematoma, postpartum depression, and decreased maternal breastfeeding (Vallejo & Zakowski, 2022). Therefore, a thorough, standardized informed consent that includes patient education on PDPH risk and management is vital to improving the quality of life of the post neuraxial peripartum patient.

To standardize the epidural informed consent process, education, and training are imperative. Changing nurse anesthesia practice requires education on the importance of the change. In recent years, nurse anesthesia education has migrated from strictly in-person instruction to a hybrid of face-to-face didactic and online learning (Pecka et al., 2014). Analysis of this shift in learning methodology has shown that education modules effectively improve practitioners' knowledge and skill level in evidence-based practice (Sapri et al., 2022). Thus,

standardizing epidural informed consent for the anesthesia provider via an evidence-based education module increases the provider's knowledge and skill and improves postpartum patient outcomes.

The definition of informed consent is the process of discussing the procedure to be performed, and the risks, benefits, and alternatives to the patient (Blumenreich, 1998). Informed consent ensures that the patient maintains their right to two ethical principles: medical autonomy and self-decision (AANA, 2016). Lack of thorough informed consent results in legal implications for the CRNA and poor patient outcomes (AANA, 2016). Informed consent is important for any patient population, but the obstetrical patient population poses specific barriers to obtaining complete informed consent.

The labor and delivery specialty is fast-paced and unpredictable. Unpredictable labor progression, complexity, and urgency of procedures are all common for the CRNA to manage anesthetically. However, these are barriers to obtaining informed consent. Providers can feel rushed during urgent or emergent labor situations, resulting in incomplete informed consent. In addition, the amount of informed consent recalls the patient may or may not have while experiencing labor pain is something the CRNA must consider (Broaddus & Chandrasekhar, 2011). One way to combat these barriers to neuraxial informed consent is to standardize its process. This standardization is a way to avoid missing any information given to the patient during a rushed encounter and improve informed consent recall (Clarke et al., 2018). Standardizing neuraxial informed consent is imperative to uphold the patient's right to be informed of the complications of neuraxial anesthesia, including PDPH.

PDPH Pathophysiology

A PDPH occurs when there is a compromise in the dural sac. This compromise from neuraxial anesthesia causes cerebral spinal fluid (CSF) to leak from the epidural space into the paravertebral space (Ljubisavljevic, 2020). The leaking of CSF and the body's inability to quickly replace the lost volume results in CSF hypovolemia. This hypovolemia causes tension on intracranial nerves and vasculature, resulting in a PDPH (Ljubisavljevic, 2020).

PDPH symptoms include cephalgia, diplopia, nausea, and photophobia. More recent literature has identified long-term consequences of PDPH, including postpartum depression, post-traumatic stress disorder, chronic headaches, backaches, and decreased breastfeeding success (Orbach-Zinger et al., 2021).

Diagnosis of PDPH

The International Headache Institution defines PDPH as a headache within five days of a dural puncture (Vallejo & Zakowski, 2022). Not all patients who experience a suspected accidental dural puncture (ADP) will develop a PDPH. Statistically, 50-80% do (Buddeberg et al., 2019). According to the American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA), all patients with suspected ADP should be assessed for signs of PDPH within 24 hours (ASA, 2021). Follow-up assessment of symptoms of PDPH in patients with suspected ADP leads to early diagnosis of PDPH and treatment. Symptoms for patients with PDPH were seen up to six months after their ADP, reinforcing the importance of follow-up assessments on these patients (Ansari et al., 2021).

Treatment of PDPH

PDPH and its sequelae are treatable. Invasive and noninvasive approaches are available to patients with symptoms of PDPH. An epidural blood patch (EBP) is the current gold standard for treating PDPH and is 77-96% effective (Russell et al., 2019; Vallejo & Zakowski, 2022).

Early treatment and the prevention of long-term consequences of PDPH for the postpartum patient are only attainable with the identification and diagnosis of PDPH. The sooner patients receive an EBP, the less likely they are to develop long-term effects. Therefore, early identification and treatment of patients with PDPH improve obstetrical patient outcomes.

Neuraxial anesthesia-related ADP occurs in 0.15-1.5% of parturients (Buddeberg et al., 2019). Of these patients, up to 80% develop PDPH (Buddeberg et al., 2019). Short-term consequences of PDPH include increased patient morbidity, readmission, and length of stay (LOS) (Orbach-Zinger et al., 2021). Within recent years, research has identified new long-term medical and mental sequelae (Orbach-Zinger et al., 2021). In addition, a retrospective cohort study by Guglielminotti et al. (2019) found that serious neurological consequences exist for patients with PDPH, including cerebral embolism and subdural hematoma. All these symptoms decrease the quality of life of the postpartum patient and are risks of neuraxial anesthetics that should be discussed within an informed consent (AANA, 2016)

There is no current standard of practice for informed consent for epidural placement. However, it is identified in the literature that early identification and treatment, compared to late recognition and treatment, results in decreased LOS and incidence of symptom reoccurrence (Santos et al., 2023). Hence, healthcare providers must have a consistent, standardized, informed consent process for patients to intervene in PDPH treatment early and improve patient outcomes.

In summary, the debilitating headache and complication of neuraxial anesthesia is linked to short- and long-term consequences for the postpartum patient. Although PDPH is an unforeseen risk of neuraxial anesthesia, patient education regarding PDPH results in patients accessing treatment sooner and potentially avoiding the sequelae of PDPH (Vallejo & Zakowski, 2022). While an EBP is 97% effective for the first attempt, some patient populations would

refuse an EBP due to religious affiliations (Olsen et al., 2018; Vallejo & Zakowski, 2022). When discussing this during the informed consent process, it is imperative to inform the patient of the potential complications and whether the treatment goes against their religious beliefs. Issues like Jehovah's Witness patients refusing an EBP is an issue that can arise due to the lack of thorough standardized informed consent. Therefore, standardized informed consent practice is essential to maintaining a patient's right to medical decision-making.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice scholarly project was to improve the epidural informed consent process for CRNAs at Kaiser Permanente San Bernardino County by implementing an educational module emphasizing a standardized epidural informed consent to include PDPH education for laboring parturients. This educational module resulted in more CRNAs providing thorough informed consent and patient education regarding PDPH, as online learning has improved clinicians' knowledge and skill in evidence-based practice (Sapri et al., 2022). This imperative patient education leads to early identification and treatment of PDPH to improve short- and long-term patient outcomes. The purpose was achieved by a) improving CRNA epidural informed consent practices; and b) reeducate CRNAs on the short- and long-term effects of PDPH for patients.

Supporting Framework – Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice

The Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care (Buckwater et al., 2017) was used to guide the development and implementation of this project (Figure 1). The Iowa Model has been used extensively to successfully guide evidence-based practice innovations since its inception in the 1990's. The Model was developed by a group of nurses at the University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics in collaboration with nursing

faculty from the University of Iowa. The model underwent several revisions with the last revision published in 2017 (Buckwater et al., 2017).

The Iowa Model-Revised has seven steps and three decision points. The first step is identifying a clinical problem that needs to be resolved. The clinical problem identified for this DNP project was the lack of a standardized neuraxial PDPH informed consent process at Kaiser Permanente San Bernardino County (KPSBC). The quality improvement team within KPSBC aided in the identification of this issue, as the incidence of complaints of PDPH in obstetrical (OB) patients was on the rise within this facility (M. Shaw, personal communication, March 1, 2023). The second step in the Iowa Model-Revised calls for formulating a purpose statement. The purpose of this project was to improve the epidural informed consent process for CRNAs at Kaiser Permanente San Bernardino County by implementing an educational module emphasizing a standardized epidural informed consent to include PDPH education for laboring parturients. This improvement in nurse anesthesia practice and patient care aligns with the organization's philosophy of providing high-quality care (Kaiser Permanente, 2018).

Using the Iowa model as a guide, the next step in this project's implementation was identifying a multidisciplinary team. The multidisciplinary team for this project included the KPSBC Chief of Anesthesia, the Department Administrator, the department of anesthesia staff scheduler, and the Quality Improvement team comprised of two staff anesthesiologists (Dr. Joshua Milius and Dr. Amir Golsorkhi) and one CRNA (Matthew Shaw CRNA). Together, this team can identify trends and improvements in nurse anesthesia practice within the KPSBC anesthesia department.

Following the Iowa Model, the next included appraising, and synthesizing the literature on this topic. The project can be implemented if there is compelling evidence to support its

implementation. The literature search process, search results, and synthesis of the literature are described in the next section of this paper.

Designing and piloting the practice change is the next step. Phase One of this project included a pre-education module survey. The pre-education module survey had three parts. Part 1 consisted of questions soliciting demographic data. Part 2 was an open-ended response exploring participants' perceptions of and barriers to providing adequate informed consent. Part 3 contained items outlined in the tool developed by Spatz et al. (2020) to establish a minimum standard for informed consent documents (Appendix B). For each participant, an informed consent pre-module quality score was calculated based on the suggested scoring approach developed by Spatz et al. (2020).

In Phase Two, an education module with evidence-based recommendations for PDPH informed consent processes was created. The same group of staff nurse anesthetists that will complete this module will then complete Phase Three of this project, which is the same survey as a post-intervention evaluation. This final phase will give insight into the effectiveness of the intervention by comparing the pre- and post-intervention surveys.

The last step of the Iowa model is disseminating the project's findings, which goes outside the project's timeline. If this project's results determine that the education module is effective in improving practice, this education module will be disseminated to the California State University at Fullerton (CSUF) cohort 11 on dissemination day, at the CSUF College of Health and Human Development Student Research Showcase, Western Institute of Nursing, Sigma Theta Tau, and CRNA professional organization meetings.

Review of Literature

Search Strategies

A literature search was completed using the following scholarly databases: CINAHL, PubMed, Science Direct, Sage Journals Premier, and Wiley Online Library. The search terms "informed consent" and "anesthesia" yielded 158 peer-reviewed articles in CINAHL and 1023 articles on PubMed. Adding the search term "standardized" yielded six articles on CINAHL and 153 articles on PubMed. Other combinations of search terms used were: neuraxial informed consent, patient education, computer-based training, and PDPH consent. Subject headings for the search included: anesthesia, computer-based training, dural puncture, neuraxial complications, and consent. Initially, the criteria for the literature search were limited to a publication date from 2017-2023. However, studies between 2013-2023 were of higher quality evidence and quantity. Using these terms and criteria, the literature review included four systematic reviews (Broaddus & Chandrasekhar, 2011; Smith et al., 2018; Wada et al., 2019; Wilson & Burkle, 2020), two randomized controlled trials (Lee et al., 2019; Taylor et al., 2021), one single nonrandomized study (Burkle et al., 2017), one prospective clinical study (Bashir et al., 2021), one modified Delphi study (Tanaka et al., 2016), one prospective, randomized, single-blind trial (Antoniou et al., 2018), and one mixed methods pilot study (Shoemaker et al., 2018).

The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice scholarly project was to improve the epidural informed consent process for CRNAs at Kaiser Permanente San Bernardino County by implementing an educational module emphasizing a standardized epidural informed consent to include PDPH education for laboring parturients. This section presents the results of the literature review on improving epidural consent practice by identifying four critical subtopics:

informed consent, parturient informed consent, informed consent standardization, and practice change education.

Informed Consent

The AANA maintains a code of ethics for CRNAs. The AANA's policy and practice guidelines for informed consent for all practicing CRNAs are subcategories of their code of ethics (AANA, 2016). These guidelines emphasize CRNAs' ethical responsibility to provide all patients with thorough, informed consent (AANA, 2016; Burkle et al., 2013). These guidelines have ethical and legal implications and can be applied to any anesthetic procedure the CRNA performs. The subject of CRNA informed consent practice has significant legal consequences at the local, state, and federal levels (AANA, 2016), and thus should not be taken lightly. Nurse anesthesia accreditation standards and facility policies must also be considered in informed consent practices (AANA, 2016).

To avoid legal repercussions, the anesthesia provider must adhere to two components of informed consent (AANA, 2016). The first component is the ethical principle of personal autonomy, which means that patients have the right to know what procedure will be performed (AANA, 2016). The second component of informed consent is self-determination and self-decision (AANA, 2016). Patients must agree to the potential risks associated with the procedure (AANA, 2016). With these two ethical components in mind, the AANA recognizes the four-step informed consent process (AANA, 2016).

The first step in the informed consent process is ensuring patient competence and capacity and explaining the procedure (AANA, 2016; Wilson & Burkle, 2020). This step maintains that the anesthesia provider identifies that the patient is legally and mentally capable of making their own healthcare decisions. Once the patient is identified as competent and capable,

the anesthesia provider must describe the following components of the procedure to be performed: what the procedure is and its purpose; any risks, benefits, and side effects of the procedure; alternatives to the procedure; and the risks of declining the procedure (AANA, 2016; Broaddus & Chandrasekhar, 2011). The provider should avoid expressing any personal bias while describing these components (Wilson & Burkle, 2020).

Next, CRNAs must ensure that the patient understands the procedure. Once evident that the patient has thoroughly comprehended the information, the patient must voluntarily agree to the procedure. Once they have agreed, the final step is to document the discussion and agreement between the anesthesia provider and patient (AANA, 2016). All four of these components of informed consent are mandatory for any anesthetic procedure, including neuraxial anesthesia (AANA, 2016).

In summary, studies on this topic show the critical ethical and legal implications of completing a thorough informed consent. Providing comprehensive informed consent is not always easy. For example, the obstetrical anesthesia population poses unique challenges in implementing informed consent for the parturient (AANA, 2016; Wilson & Burkle, 2020).

Parturient Informed Consent

The challenges surrounding neuraxial informed consent for neuraxial labor are well documented within the literature. Medical capacity, or the ability of a patient to understand and retain information during informed consent, is the primary issue anesthesia providers face when consenting to this patient population (AANA 2016; Broaddus & Chandrasekhar, 2011). Ideally, anesthesia-informed consent for the parturient should be obtained during the prenatal period (AANA, 2016). Providing prenatal patients with education before the onset of labor has been shown to set expectations and increase positive experiences of labor (AANA 2016). Despite

evidence supporting the importance of prenatal education, informed consent is routinely done during active labor (AANA, 2016)

Current literature identifies two aspects of obtaining neuraxial informed consent during active labor. The first is the patient's perspective. The patient's socioeconomic status, primary language, and education level all impact the informed consent process. A US study showed that 80 out of 82 women stated that active labor did not affect their decision-making (Fröhlich et al., 2011; Wilson & Burkle, 2020). On the other hand, a study in Ireland stated that 79% of women believed that the pain associated with their labor made them incapable of providing consent (Gerancher et al., 2000; Wilson & Burkle, 2020).

The second aspect is the anesthesia provider's perception of whether the parturient can provide consent (Wilson & Burkle, 2020). Like the first, there are mixed results in the literature. In a study performed in Canada, New Zealand, and Australia, 70% of providers thought that active labor affects the parturient's ability to consent (Wilson & Burkle, 2020). While in the United States, 68% of anesthesia providers believe that women can consent during labor (Wilson & Burkle, 2020).

The discrepancy in literature is due to the subjective nature of pain and perceptions. Although important to consider, both aspects of patient and provider perceptions while obtaining neuraxial informed consent during active labor should not be the sole consideration when it comes to the decision-making capacity of the parturient (Wilson & Burkle, 2020).

Inconsistencies in the literature could be due to the fact that most studies addressing parturient informed consent used recall as their primary measure (Wilson & Burkle, 2020). A systematic review addressed the current literature on the parturient's ability to recall informed consent information during active labor (Wada et al., 2019). Within the systematic review's 20

studies, there was overwhelming evidence to support that labor pain does not affect the parturient's ability to recall the risks of neuraxial anesthesia (Wada et al., 2019).

In conclusion, there is a multitude of reasons that CRNAs are not obtaining PDPH informed consent in current practice. The barriers to obtaining informed consent for laboring patients include the patient's perception that they cannot provide consent due to pain and the provider's perception that the patient cannot comprehend due to pain (Wilson & Burkle, 2020). Although research on parturient informed consent shows inconsistent patient and provider perceptions of parturient's mental capacity, peripartum patients can recall elements of their neuraxial informed consent similarly to other patients (Wada et al., 2019). To improve this recall for PDPH informed consent, standardized neuraxial anesthesia informed consent methods would provide consistent, thorough patient education and an added element of patient safety (Broaddus & Chandrasekhar, 2011).

Informed Consent Standardization

Many hospitals do not have a standardized method of anesthesia-informed consent training (Antoniou et al., 2018). This lack of training leads to inconsistent methods of informed consent processes. A systematic review by Broaddus and Chandrasekhar (2011) found that anesthesia providers from 12 academic facilities included common risks of neuraxial anesthesia and omit severe risks altogether when discussing informed consent with patients. Standardizing these details of informed consent is vital to maintaining patient participation in their medical care, protecting the anesthesia provider from the legal implications of incomplete informed consent, and increasing CRNA compliance to complete a thorough PDPH informed consent (Bashir et al., 2021). In a prospective study by Clarke et al. (2018), standardized verbal and

written informed consent materials increased information retention and recall of surgical patients. (Clarke et al., 2018).

Barriers to the strategies for standardizing the informed consent process are human error, rushed encounters with patients, and the providers' attempt not to instill fear in the patient (Antoniou et al., 2018; Burkle et al., 2013). Discussing common and uncommon risks is shown in the literature to be patients' preference, despite the anxiety it may give patients to be educated on the risks (Burkle et al., 2013). Although the anesthesia provider may omit certain procedure risks to reduce the patient's anxiety, they must hold the patient's right to medical decision-making at the forefront and disclose all pertinent risks (Burkle et al., 2013). Hence, it is the laboring patient's right to be informed about the incidence, signs, and symptoms of PDPH, a risk following neuraxial labor analgesia.

In conclusion, the literature shows that standardizing PDPH informed consent practice upholds the laboring patients' medical right to consent, protects providers from legal issues, increases patients' recall, increases patient-provider trust, and improves the overall patient experience (Bashir et al., 2021; Burkle et al., 2017; Clarke et al., 2018). By standardizing patient education during the informed consent process on neuraxial anesthesia, specifically PDPH, patients can be thoroughly educated on its risks, such as PDPH and its sequelae, which directly affect patient outcomes (Bashir et al., 2021; Tanaka et al., 2016).

Patient Safety

Standardized PDPH informed consent techniques increase patient safety (Bashir et al., 2021). In a prospective observational cohort study by DelPizzo et al. (2020), preoperative education on PDPH during informed consent for neuraxial anesthesia decreased patient stress and led to patients managing mild symptoms of PDPH at home. Although there is not an

abundance of literature on patient safety related to PDPH standardized consent, current literature shows that standardized informed consent with "teach back" methods improves patients' ability to recall elements of the informed consent process (Shoemaker et al., 2018). Therefore, improving the patient's recall of PDPH signs and symptoms mentioned during the informed consent leads to a patient's ability to identify these signs and symptoms when experiencing them. Improved recall would lead to earlier self-recognition and diagnosis of PDPH and possibly earlier hospital intervention.

Practice Change Education

Education and training are necessary to improve patient safety by implementing standardized PDPH informed consent. Simulation and education modules are effective methods of informed consent education and training for anesthesia providers (Bashir et al., 2021; Tanaka et al., 2016). Providers will have increased knowledge and performance of informed consent processes by using andragogical principles of adult education, such as problem-oriented, experienced-based, and collaborative learning methods (Decelle, 2016). Gaps in current knowledge need to be identified before implementing learning methods and education modules to improve practice.

Identifying knowledge gaps in informed consent is critical to practice changes for anesthesia providers (Shoemaker et al., 2018). The knowledge gap of inconsistent neuraxial informed consent is not uncommon (Antoniou et al., 2018; Shoemaker et al., 2018). Identifying and addressing these gaps increases patient safety (Shoemaker et al., 2018). For example, Shoemaker et al. (2018) found that over 20% of clinicians did not think patient misunderstanding during the informed consent was a serious patient safety concern.

Education modules can close informed consent knowledge gaps (Shoemaker et al., 2018). Once the specific knowledge gap is identified, educating clinicians via education modules is essential in changing practice. The Joint Commission Journal on Quality and Patient Safety found that informed consent needed improvement (Shoemaker et al., 2018). They piloted an education module to improve informed consent practices at four hospitals. While the education improved knowledge among staff and leadership, many clinicians were still not using methods like the "teach-back" method to ensure the patients understood the procedure described to them, which shows a further need for education on this matter (Shoemaker et al., 2018). Shoemaker et al. and National Quality Forum endorse the "teach back" method of patient education in the informed consent process as the safest method of informed consent practice (2018). Overall, the lack of a consistent, informed consent practice is a problem many hospitals struggle with, and its improvement increases patient autonomy and safety (Antoniou et al., 2018; Shoemaker et al., 2018).

Summary

In conclusion, CRNAs are ethically responsible for providing informed consent for neuraxial anesthesia. Due to many barriers during the PDPH informed consent, anesthesia providers may unintentionally omit portions of this informed consent process. Literature shows that standardizing informed consent increases patients' ability to recall the risks of neuraxial anesthesia, including PDPH. By increasing recall of neuraxial risks, patients may seek care sooner for its signs and symptoms. Education and CRNA training are imperative to implement a standardized PDPH informed consent practice change.

Methods

This pilot study was a pre-post intervention evaluation based on an abstraction tool and suggested scoring approach developed by the British Journal of Medicine (BJM) (Spatz et al., 2020) to assess the quality of PDPH informed consent of participating CRNAs at Kaiser Permanente San Bernardino County (KPSBC). This pilot study was completed with CRNAs most frequently assigned to provide neuraxial anesthesia to the obstetrical patient population at KPSBC between April 2022 and April 2023. Eligible participants were identified by obtaining a descriptive report through the scheduling software Qgenda (Atlanta, Georgia), for the period between April 2022 and April 2023. This report helped determine which CRNAs completed the majority of OB shifts within the timeframe. CRNAs who agreed to participate completed an informed consent to participate in the project. Project participants were then asked via email to complete the pre-education module Qualtrics survey, a 15-minute education module, and a post-education module survey. The principal investigator for this project obtained approval to use the pre-and post-intervention survey instrument from the tool's developers. The education module focused on the ethical requirements of informed consent, specifically aimed at improving laboring patients' informed consent for PDPH.

Participants and Setting

This pilot study included a convenience sample of 15 CRNAs from KPSBC. Participants were CRNAs who were frequently scheduled (e.g., an average of 12 or more scheduled shifts per year) within the obstetrical specialty service at KPSBC and had medical staff privileges to perform epidural anesthesia at KPSBC. CRNAs rarely scheduled within the obstetrical specialty service (i.e., an average of less than 12 scheduled shifts per year) were excluded. Permission to conduct this project was obtained from the Chief of Anesthesia for KPSBC and the Anesthesia

Director for KPSBC (i.e., department administrator). The project was determined to be exempt from review by the KP Southern California and California State University, Fullerton Institutional Review Boards.

Intervention Methods

The intervention for this project had three phases. Phase One included a pre-education module survey. Phase Two required that each participant completes the education module. Phase Three consisted of a post-education module survey. The pre-education module and post-module surveys were created and sent to participants' KP email addresses using the online survey platform Qualtrics. To match participants' pre- and post-education survey results, each participant randomly selected a numbered sticker before starting the pre-education module survey. Participants then entered their number with their pre-education and post-education module responses. This methodology allowed matching participants' pre-education module and post-module responses. The collected data was password protected, remained confidential, will be stored for three years after the project's completion, and destroyed thereafter.

The pre-education module survey (Appendix C) was sent to participants three weeks before the educational module's implementation. The pre-education module survey had three parts. Part one collected demographic data from the participants: age, sex, and years worked as a CRNA. Part two was an open-ended response exploring participants' current perceptions of and barriers to providing adequate informed consent. Part three was a proctored informed consent by the project's investigator. The proctored informed consent was evaluated using the items outlined in the tool developed by Spatz et al. (2020) to establish a minimum standard for informed consent documents (Appendix B). The observation evaluation explored whether participants

complied with the minimum standards. For each participant, a pre-education module quality score was calculated based on the suggested scoring approach developed by Spatz et al. (2020).

Phase Two of this project included the intervention of a 10-15-minute education module about evidenced-based PDPH informed consent practice created and presented via Articulate 360 (Articulate Global Inc., New York, NY). Articulate 360 is an education module development program commonly used by Kaiser Permanente, although not an internally owned program. The educational module for this project was developed using the information and format of a similar educational module related to informed consent by the Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (AHRQ). Information for this project's educational module was obtained via the previously discussed literature review regarding informed consent and PDPH (Shoemaker & Brach, 2020). The information within these modules focused on training providers to communicate concisely and understandably the procedure's risks, benefits, and harms. It also includes how to communicate any alternatives to the procedure and the risks and benefits of the alternatives (Shoemaker & Brach, 2020). Communicating that no intervention is an option for the patient during the informed consent process is also highlighted within the AHRQ education modules (Shoemaker & Brach, 2020).

A consultation with the quality improvement team (i.e., two physician anesthesiologists, one CRNA, and the Chief of Anesthesia) at KPSBC was performed to solicit educational module content specific to the KPSBC population (e.g., socioeconomic demographics, religious preferences, perceived bias against neuraxial anesthesia). Approval from the AHRQ was obtained to use their informed consent education module as a guideline for this intervention (Shoemaker & Brach, 2020).

The education module was offered as voiceover PowerPoint (Microsoft Inc., Redmond, WA) slides based on the effective AHRQ informed consent module format and included the following content (Shoemaker & Brach, 2020):

- Informed consent ethics and responsibility
- Parturient comprehension of neuraxial informed consent
- PDPH informed consent barriers
- PDPH short- and long-term consequences
- Example of thorough PDPH informed consent practice

In Phase Three, participants completed a post-education module survey. A question in the survey asked the participant to confirm the completion of the education module. Next, each participant's epidural informed consent was proctored during their next scheduled shift where they had the opportunity to provide informed consent for PDPH. Their performance of the informed consent was scored using the items outlined in the tool developed by Spatz et al. (2020). The post-educational module survey results assessed participants' informed consent after the education module intervention. Comparing the pre-education module and post-education module results explored the effectiveness of the epidural anesthesia informed consent intervention (i.e., PDPH education module).

Instruments

Two instruments were used to collect data for this pilot study. The first is a demographic survey, as shown in Appendix C. A second instrument was an abstraction tool and suggested scoring approach developed by BJM to improve informed consent practice (Spatz et al., 2020) (Appendix B).

Demographics Survey

Part one of the pre-intervention survey solicited participant demographic data, including age, sex, and years working as a CRNA. These components allowed descriptive and quantitative statistical analysis of the sample. Part two of the pre-intervention survey included an open-ended response. This part enabled qualitative analysis exploring participants' perceptions of and barriers to providing adequate informed consent.

Informed Consent Abstraction Tool and Scoring Approach

An informed consent abstraction tool and scoring approach created by the BJM was used to identify knowledge gaps in participants' knowledge and practice of informed consent (Spatz et al., 2020). This tool was developed to improve and standardize informed consent documents given to patients for elective procedures and has six categories to assess the completeness of informed consent. These categories include the procedure's description, rationale, patient-centered benefit(s), probability of procedure-specific risks, procedure alternatives, and timing of informed consent (Spatz et al., 2020). Each category has one to three questions with a scoring system. The answer "yes" receives one or two points depending on the question, the answer "no" receives zero points, and questions not applicable also receive a zero.

This tool's reliability was tested in two phases. The first included training two raters with a one-hour training video on how to rate informed consent using the tool. The raters then did ten practice informed consent ratings and were given feedback on their instrument evaluation. Then, the raters assessed informed consent documents in 25 hospitals (Spatz et al., 2020). Their inter-rater agreement for over 250 documents each was 92-100%, showing consistency among the evaluators of this instrument. Spearman's correlation coefficient was used to determine construct validity. The Spearman's coefficient was 0.91, indicating a strong correlation (Schober et al.,

2018). The Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services have made this tool available for quality improvement (Spatz et al., 2020).

Data Collection

Hyperlinks to the pre-education module and post-module surveys were sent to 15 participants using their KP email addresses and the Qualtrics platform. Responses were tracked confidentially to match the pre-education module and post-module survey results for comparative analysis. The participants had four weeks to complete the education module and post-module survey. An email reminder was sent to participants at the end of every week.

Data Analysis and Evaluation

Intellectus Statistics (2019) was used for data analysis, including a paired or dependent *t*-test statistical analysis. The statistical data analysis compared participants' pre- and post-education intervention evaluation composite scores of informed consent performance with the statistical significance level set at $p < .05$. In addition to the *t*-test analysis, Pearson correlation was used to analyze the participant's scores with their demographic data to assess whether demographic attributes correlated with evaluation performance scores.

Using this statistical analysis, this project evaluated the participants' pre- and post-education module intervention informed consent scores. The practice change was assessed by comparing the participants' scores before and after they were educated on the importance of standardized PDPH informed consent practices. Other factors in learning and practice changes were evaluated by comparing the demographic data with the effectiveness of the education module (pre- and post-intervention scores).

Results

Fifteen obstetrical CRNAs completed all three phases of data collection. Participants included eight males and seven females, with the average years worked as a CRNA of 11.93 years ($SD = 5.40$). The participants completed a pre-education module survey and informed consent observation audit, completed the education module, and completed the post-education module survey and informed consent audit. Appendix D and E show a summary of the participant demographic data.

The mean preintervention informed consent audit score was 5.40 ($SD \pm 2.32$) out of a possible score of 20. The postintervention informed consent audit score's mean was 9.40 ($SD \pm 2.35$); this difference was statistically significant ($t = , p < 0.01$). The relationship between pre- and post-education module audit scores and years worked as a CRNA, age, and sex were analyzed using Pearson correlation analysis. There were no significant correlations between demographic data and participant score variables. Appendix F shows the scatterplot results of the Pearson correlation analysis.

Data saturation was achieved quickly for the qualitative portion of this project. The majority of participants stated that the barrier to thorough consent practice at KPSAC was consenting late in the parturients' labor process. When discussing ways to improve, participants stated that early consent practice would be their recommendation. Both of these answers lead to the same solution. Providers believe that the earlier the informed consent is completed in the labor process, the less pain that parturient will be in and the more thorough the informed consent.

Discussion

The statistically significant improvement of participants' audit scores is consistent with results reported in the literature. With formal education on thorough informed consent practice, providers have high-quality informed consent practice (Lee et al., 2019). This is congruent with the findings of this project, as both highlight the importance of standardizing the informed consent process for epidural anesthesia. Standardizing informed consent decreases the accidental omission of key components of informed consent and improves its quality (Bashir et al., 2021; Burkle et al., 2017; Clarke et al., 2018). By improving the quality of informed consent quality, shared decision-making improves the quality of patient-centered care (Kunneman & Montori, 2017). The effectiveness of the education module in reminding providers (with an average of almost 12 years of experience) of the essential components of informed consent was shown in the statistically significant improved audit scores.

When comparing the pre-and post-educational module informed consent audits, many providers had a memorized informed consent process that they altered once they completed the education module and identified what components of their consistent informed consent were missing. This emphasizes the importance of teaching student registered nurse anesthetists (SRNAs) the key components of consent within the clinical setting (Antoniou et al., 2018; Lee et al., 2019). As clinicians, we learn from our clinical experiences as preceptors teach them. For example, if an SRNA is taught and memorizes an incomplete informed consent process, that student may continue this incomplete informed consent into their practice. Reminding current CRNAs of the key components of informed consent throughout this project improved the quality of informed consent practice, improving the example these providers will set for SRNAs learning informed consent practices (Antoniou et al., 2018).

Without thorough informed consent, the elements of patient education are missed. Patients are more consistently educated on PDPH risk, signs and symptoms, and treatment modalities through standardizing epidural informed consent. The improved audit scores show that the education module effectively improved the verbal components of epidural informed consent. The patient education elements were less likely to be missed after providers were re-educated on the required elements of informed consent.

Limitations

The dynamic nature of the labor and delivery unit poses a unique limitation to informed consent, and this project identified this as a limitation to the study. Some participants completed the pre-education module audit, the education module, and the post-education module all within the same shift. Due to the inconsistency of women in need of epidurals in the labor and delivery unit, other participants had large gaps of time between the education module and the post-education module audit. These large time gaps affected the results as the participants who completed the module and could immediately put it into practice had an advantage over those who did not and may have scored higher on the audit.

Another limitation of this study was that the principal investigator completed the audits. This data collection process adds the potential element of bias within the study's data collection and its results. Due to project time constraints, this was an unavoidable data collection element. The Hawthorne effect was also a limitation to data collection within this study, as participants knew they were being audited during their informed consent processes, resulting in a possible improved performance.

Recommendations for Practice

The results from this project emphasize the importance of standardizing informed consent practice. By standardizing informed consent practice, providers are less likely to accidentally omit components of epidural informed consent, including patient education for PDPH (Clarke et al., 2018). By obtaining complete informed consent for epidural anesthesia, patients have an increased knowledge of the procedure and its potential complications, such as PDPH. With patients knowledgeable on PDPH, its signs and symptoms, and treatments from their informed consent, early detection and both conservative and invasive intervention is possible. Reeducating providers on the legal responsibility and explicit components of thorough informed consent practice can therefore improve practice and patient outcomes.

Standardization is not easy with experienced providers, as they have been practicing informed consent for years, which is a barrier to any change of practice (Clarke et al., 2018). According to Lewin's change theory, creating a practice change requires unfreezing current practice and creating a motivation to move forward with the change for it to be successful (Zaccagnini & Pechacek, 2021). Therefore, an effective strategy for a change in practice to standardization informed consent is to educate SRNAs on how to obtain thorough informed consent for epidural anesthesia. Cultivating a habit of appropriate informed consent practice is one strategy for improving informed consent practice (Antoniou et al., 2018).

Lastly, early informed consent practice is to be considered. Obtaining informed consent upon arrival to the hospital while parturients are in the earlier stages of labor will decrease the interruptions of informed consent due to pain during labor contractions. The lack of interruptions increases the completeness of epidural informed consent practice and the lack of accidental omission of key components.

Conclusion

PDPH is a real and serious risk of epidural anesthesia. The short and long-term sequelae are not benign to parturients and postpartum women. Education on the signs and symptoms and treatment options for PDPH increases patient knowledge on how to get early treatment, potentially avoiding the long-term sequelae associated with PDPH. This education should be provided during epidural informed consent.

Informed consent for the parturient in active labor poses challenges for the anesthesia provider. As the patient is in pain, the consent may be rushed and interrupted by labor contraction pain. This scenario can lead to accidentally omitting components, including patient education about PDPH. As evidenced by the results of this project, reeducation of anesthesia providers is one way to improve and standardize informed consent practice. By improving this practice, parturients are well informed of the procedure, its risks and benefits, and treatment options associated with the risks. Therefore, improving informed consent practice for epidural anesthesia increases parturient knowledge and improves patient outcomes.

References

American Association for Nurse Anesthetists. (2016, July). Informed consent for anesthesia care.

[https://www.aana.com/docs/default-source/practiceaana-com-web-documents-\(all\)/professional-practice-manual/standards-for-nurse-anesthesia-practice.pdf?sfvrsn=e00049b1_18](https://www.aana.com/docs/default-source/practiceaana-com-web-documents-(all)/professional-practice-manual/standards-for-nurse-anesthesia-practice.pdf?sfvrsn=e00049b1_18)

American Society of Anesthesiologists. (2021, October 13). Statement on post-dural puncture headache management. <https://www.asahq.org/standards-and-guidelines/statement-on-post-dural-puncture-headache-management>

Ansari, J. R., Barad, M., Shafer, S., & Flood, P. (2021). Chronic disabling postpartum headache after unintentional dural puncture during epidural anaesthesia: A prospective cohort study. *British Journal of Anaesthesia*, 127(4), 600–607

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bja.2021.05.020>

Antoniou, A., Marmai, K., Qasem, F., Cherry, R., Jones, P. M., & Singh, S. (2018). Educating anesthesia residents to obtain and document informed consent for epidural labor analgesia: Does simulation play a role?. *International Journal of Obstetric Anesthesia*,

34, 79–84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijoa.2017.12.005>

Bashir, M. A., Khan, A. A., & Khan, S. A. (2021). Assessment of informed consent and the impact of simulation on anesthesia trainees. *Cureus*, 13(11), e19787.

<https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.19787>

Broadus, B. M., & Chandrasekhar, S. (2011). Informed consent in obstetric anesthesia.

Anesthesia and analgesia, 112(4), 912–915.

<https://doi.org/10.1213/ANE.0b013e31820e777a>

- Buckwalter, K. C., Cullen, L., Hanrahan, K., Kleiber, C., McCarthy, A. M., Rakel, B., Steelman, V., Tripp, R. T., & Tucker, S. (2017). Iowa model of evidence-based practice: Revisions and validation. *Worldviews on Evidence-Based Nursing, 14*(3), 175–182. <https://doi.org/10.1111/wvn.12223>
- Buddeberg, B. S., Bandschapp, O., & Girard, T. (2019). Post-dural puncture headache. *Minerva Anestesiologica, 85*(5), 543–553. <https://doi.org/10.23736/S0375-9393.18.13331-1>
- Burkle, C. M., Olsen, D. A., Sviggum, H. P., & Jacob, A. K. (2017). Parturient recall of neuraxial analgesia risks: Impact of labor pain vs no labor pain. *Journal of Clinical Anesthesia, 36*, 158–163. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinane.2016.10.033>
- Burkle, C.M., Pasternak, J.J., Armstrong, M.H., & Keegan, M.T. (2013). Patient perspectives on informed consent for anaesthesia and surgery: American attitudes. *Acta Anaesthesiologica Scandinavica, 57*(3), 342–349. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aas.12037>
- Clarke, K., O'Loughlin, P., & Cashman, J. (2018). Standardized consent: The effect of information sheets on information retention. *Journal of Patient Safety, 14*(2), e25–e28. <https://doi.org/10.1097/PTS.0000000000000230>
- Decelle, G. (2016). Andragogy: A fundamental principle of online education for nursing. *Journal of Best Practices in Health Professions Diversity: Education, Research & Policy, 9*(2), 1263–1273. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26554258>
- DelPizzo, K., Luu, T., Fields, K. G., Sideris, A., Dong, N., Edmonds, C., & Zayas, V. M. (2020). Risk of postdural puncture headache in adolescents and adults. *Anesthesia and Analgesia, 131*(1), 273–279. <https://doi.org/10.1213/ANE.00000000000004691>
- Fröhlich, S., Tan, T., Walsh, A., & Carey, M. (2011). Epidural analgesia for labour: maternal knowledge, preferences and informed consent. *Irish Medical Journal, 104*(10), 300–302.

- Gerancher, J. C., Grice, S. C., Dewan, D. M., & Eisenach, J. (2000). An evaluation of informed consent prior to epidural analgesia for labor and delivery. *International journal of obstetric anesthesia*, 9(3), 168–173. <https://doi.org/10.1054/ijoa.1999.0371>
- Guglielminotti, J., Landau, R., & Li, G. (2019). Major neurologic complications associated with postdural puncture headache in obstetrics: A retrospective cohort study. *Anesthesia and analgesia*, 129(5), 1328–1336. <https://doi.org/10.1213/ANE.0000000000004336>
- Intellectus Statistics. (2019). Intellectus Statistics [Online computer software]. <http://analyze.intellectusstatistics.com/>
- Kunneman, M., & Montori, V. M. (2017). When patient-centred care is worth doing well: Informed consent or shared decision-making. *BMJ Quality & Safety*, 26(7), 522–524. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjqs-2016-005969>
- Lee, S. C., Nguyen, V., Nguyen, A., Minard, C. G., & Rajagopalan, S. (2019). Teaching anesthesiology residents how to obtain informed consent. *Journal of Education in Perioperative Medicine*, 21(4), E632.
- Ljubisavljevic, S. (2020). Postdural puncture headache as a complication of lumbar puncture: Clinical manifestations, pathophysiology, and treatment. *Neurological Sciences*, 41(12), 3563–3568. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10072-020-04757-z>
- Kaiser Permanente. (2018, December). Measuring Quality. <https://healthy.kaiserpermanente.org/southern-california/pages/quality-safety/measuring-quality>
- Kaiser Permanente. (2018, July). Patient Safety. <https://healthy.kaiserpermanente.org/southern-california/pages/quality-safety/patient-safety>

- Olsen, K. R., Screws, A. L., & Vose, S. O. (2018). Blood patch in a Jehovah's witness: Case report of a novel arterial-to-epidural closed circuit technique. *Anesthesia and Analgesia Practice*, 10(8), 201–203. <https://doi.org/10.1213/XAA.0000000000000661>
- Orbach-Zinger, S., Eidelman, L. A., Livne, M. Y., Matkovski, O., Mangoubi, E., Borovich, A., Wazwaz, S. A., Ioscovich, A., Zekry, Z. H. B., Ariche, K., & Weiniger, C. F. (2021). Long-term psychological and physical outcomes of women after postdural puncture headache: A retrospective, cohort study. *European journal of anaesthesiology*, 38(2), 130–137. <https://doi.org/10.1097/EJA.0000000000001297>
- Pecka, S. L., Kotcherlakota, S., & Berger, A. M. (2014). Community of inquiry model: Advancing distance learning in nurse anesthesia education. *American Association of Nurse Anesthetists Journal*, 82(3), 212–218.
- Russell, R., Laxton, C., Lucas, D. N., Niewiarowski, J., Scrutton, M., & Stocks, G. (2019). Treatment of obstetric post-dural puncture headache. Part 2: Epidural blood patch. *International journal of obstetric anesthesia*, 38, 104–118. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijoa.2018.12.005>
- Santos, N. S., Nunes, J. M., Font, M. L., Carmona, C., & Castro, M. M. (2023). Early versus late sphenopalatine ganglion block with ropivacaine in postdural puncture headache: An observational study. *Brazilian journal of anesthesiology (Elsevier)*, 73(1), 42–45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bjane.2021.01.007>
- Sapri, N. D., Ng, Y. T., Wu, V. X., & Klainin-Yobas, P. (2022). Effectiveness of educational interventions on evidence-based practice for nurses in clinical settings: A systematic review and Meta-analysis. *Nurse Education Today*, 111, N.PAG. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2022.105295>

- Schober, P., Boer, C., & Schwarte, L. A. (2018). Correlation Coefficients: Appropriate Use and Interpretation. *Anesthesia and analgesia*, *126*(5), 1763–1768.
<https://doi.org/10.1213/ANE.0000000000002864>
- Shoemaker S, & Brach C. (2017). Implementation guide for AHRQ's making informed consent an informed choice training modules. Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality.
<https://www.ahrq.gov/health-literacy/professional-training/informed-choice/guide.html>
- Shoemaker, S. J., Brach, C., Edwards, A., Chitavi, S. O., Thomas, R., & Wasserman, M. (2018). Opportunities to improve informed consent with AHRQ training modules. *The Joint Commission Journal on Quality and Patient Safety*, *44*(6), 343–352.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcjq.2017.11.010>
- Spatz, E. S., Suter, L. G., George, E., Perez, M., Curry, L., Desai, V., Bao, H., Geary, L. L., Herrin, J., Lin, Z., Bernheim, S. M., & Krumholz, H. M. (2020). An instrument for assessing the quality of informed consent documents for elective procedures: Development and testing. *BMJ Open*, *10*(5), e033297–e033297.
<https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2019-033297>
- Tanaka, P., Park, L., & Tanaka, M. (2016). Development and testing of a curriculum for teaching informed consent for spinal anesthesia to anesthesiology residents. *Journal of Pain & Relief*, *5*(5), OMICS Publishing Group. <https://doi.org/10.4172/2167-0846.1000259>
- Trumble, J., Lee, J., Slater, P. M., Sellors, J., & Cyna, A. M. (2015). Consent for labour epidural analgesia: An observational study in a single institution. *Anaesthesia & Intensive Care*, *43*(3), 323–327. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0310057X1504300307>

- Vallejo, M. C., & Zakowski, M. I. (2022). Post-dural puncture headache diagnosis and management. *Best Practice & Research: Clinical Anaesthesiology*, 36(1), 179–189. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bpa.2022.01.002>
- Wada, K., Charland, L. C., & Bellingham, G. (2019). Can women in labor give informed consent to epidural analgesia?. *Bioethics*, 33(4), 475–486. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bioe.12517>
- Wilson, E. H., & Burkle, C. M. (2020). The meaning of consent and its implications for anesthesiologists. *Advances in Anesthesia*, 38, 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aan.2020.07.001>
- Zaccagnini, M. E., & Pechacek, J. M. (2021). *The doctor of nursing practice essentials: A new model for advanced practice nursing*. Jones & Bartlett Learning.

Appendix A

Figure 1: The Iowa Model Revised

Figure 1

Appendix B

Table 1: An Instrument for Assessing Informed Consent Quality

Table 1

Domain	Item	Response	Points
	Description of procedure		
Content/presentation	1. Is language describing <i>what</i> the procedure is (beyond the medical name) provided for the patient? (plain language)	'Yes'	2
		'No'	0
Presentation	1a. If provided, is it typed?	'Yes'	1
		'No'	0
		'N/A'	0
Content/presentation	2. Is a description of <i>how</i> the procedure will be performed provided for the patient? (plain language)	'Yes'	2
		'No'	0
Presentation	2a. If provided, is it typed?	'Yes'	1
		'No'	0
		'N/A'	0
	Rationale for procedure		
Content	3. Is the clinical rationale (condition-specific justification) for <i>why</i> the procedure will be performed provided?	'Yes, context and condition given and fully meet criteria'	2
		'Context and condition given, but do not fully meet criteria'	1
		'No, no rationale given'	0
	Patient-oriented benefit(s)		
Content	4. Is any patient-oriented <i>benefit</i> provided (intended impact on the patient's health, longevity and/or quality of life)?	'Yes'	2
		'No'	0
	Probability of procedure-specific risks		
Content	5. Is a <i>quantitative probability</i> provided for any procedure-specific <i>risk</i> ?	'Yes'	2
		'No'	0
	6. Is a <i>qualitative probability</i> provided for any procedure-specific <i>risk</i> ?	'Yes'	1
		'No'	0
	Alternative(s) to the procedures		
Content	7. Is any <i>alternative</i> provided for the patient?	'Yes'	2
		'No'	0
	Timing		
Timing	8a. Date the document was shared with the patient; if not available, the patient's/proxy's date of signature. 8b. Date of procedure. 8c. Patient opted out of receiving the consent document at least 1 day prior to the procedure.	At least 1 day before procedure <i>OR</i> patient opted out of viewing the informed consent document at least 1 day prior.	5
		Less than 1 day before procedure.	0
		Missing either date of patient's/proxy's signature or missing date of procedure.	0
	Maximum quality score		20

For item 3, either 0, 1 or 2 points are granted.
N/A, not applicable.

Appendix C

Preintervention Survey Questions

- 1) What is your age?
- 2) What is your gender?
- 3) How many years have you worked for Kaiser Permanente San Bernardino County? How many years have you been consistently providing anesthesia to the obstetrical patient?
- 4) What barriers have you encountered to performing thorough informed consent to laboring patients?
- 5) How could the informed consent process for neuraxial anesthesia (specifically postdural puncture headache) be improved upon at KPSBC?

Appendix D

Table 2: Demographic Data Results for Sex of Participants

Table 2

Frequency Table for Nominal Variables

Variable	<i>n</i>	%
Gender		
Female	7	46.67
Male	8	53.33
Missing	0	0.00

Note. Due to rounding errors, percentages may not equal 100%.

Appendix E

Table 3: Demographic Data Results for Age of Participants

Table 3

Summary Statistics Table for Interval and Ratio Variables

Variable	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>SE_M</i>	Min	Max
Age	44.87	7.67	15	1.98	33.00	59.00
Years_as_OB_CRNA	11.93	5.40	15	1.40	4.00	20.00

Appendix F

Figure 2: Pearson Correlation Scatterplot Results

Figure 2

Scatterplots with the regression line added for Years_as_OB_CRNA and SC0_PRE

